

BIOMIMETIC DESIGN OF INTERFACE FOR METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Advanced composite materials with nice properties have a promise future used as structural materials. However, study and development of metal matrix composites (MMC) have met a lot of problems, such as poor physical and chemical compatibility at the interface, fabrication process and so on. It is possible to solve those fundamental problems if the biomimetics is applied to the design of their interfaces in MMC.

The observation and analysis of the interfaces of bio-materials in the nature show the good stability, good physical and chemical compatibility as well as multi-layered and/or gradient change of structure and compositions across the interfaces. Referring these facts, an ideal interface can be designed for carbon fiber reinforced MMC systems as multi-layered and gradient compositions of pyrolytic carbon(PC)//resistant barrier//wetting layer from fiber to matrix, for example, PC//SiC//Si or PC//AlN//Al for carbon fiber reinforced aluminum alloys, and PC//TiC//Ti or PC//TiN//Ti for carbon fiber reinforced titanium alloys and so on.

1. Introduction

Great attention has been paid to the study and development of advanced composite materials(ACM) with nice properties in recent decades. Unfortunately, the study on metal matrix composites(MMC) has met a lot of problems and advances slowly owing to the poor interface and others. An ideal interface of MMC should be characterized not only by physical and chemical compatibility, but also by the good stability^[1]. A lot of researches on the interface of MMC have been carried out and rich results have been achieved^[2]. However, most results are the observation and analysis of interfaces made by individual researchers and did not solve the fundamental problems of the MMC interfaces. Fortunately, it is well known that the biomaterials in the nature are compositely structured and have been naturally selected and evolved for millions of years, such that a great variety of naturally rational composite structures with hybrid superiority had been formed, for instance, bamboo and wood have the high strength and toughness, the effective coordination among bone tendon and muscle in animals have high

mentioned above.

3.1. Choice of the resistant layer to reaction

To resist the reaction between carbon fiber and metals, it is best to add a resistant layer between them. The resistant layer must behave like:

- good thermal stability and high oxidation resistance;
- no reaction between the layer and carbon as well as between the layer and metals.
- the middle thermal expansion coefficient between carbon fibers and the matrix metals.

Refractory compounds are chosen as the candidates of resistant layer because of their adequate properties shown in Table 1⁽⁶⁾.

3.2 Choice of the wetting layer.

Wetting power of matrix to the resistant layer is related to the successful fabrication of composites with good properties and must be carefully considered. The wetting condition of a liquid to a solid suggested by Delannay et al⁽⁶⁾ is:

$$W_a > R_w \quad (1)$$

where W_a is the work of adhesion in a binding system and R_w is the surface energy of the liquid. In general, the work of adhesion for ceramic-metal system is less than 600 mJ/M² and the surface energy of a liquid metal is over 1000 mJ/M², so it is difficult to get wetting between ceramics and liquid metals. In order to meet the requirement of wetting at the interfaces, it is necessary to improve the wetting status between the matrix and the chosen resistant layer.

In the light of observation and analysis of biomaterials, the gradient change of composition from the resistant layer to matrix would eliminate the wetting problems, which can also be verified by theoretical analysis. For the MMC system, the wetting layer should be the gradient layer and the increment of constituents from the resistant layer to the matrix should be extended to the matrix or that have some solubility in matrix but not react with the matrix.

3.3 Thickness of the resistant layer.

Because the fracture strains of ceramic compounds (e.g, SiC, TiC, TiN, AlN) are smaller than that of carbon fibers in general, the ceramic coating on carbon fibers has a serious influence on the strength of CFs when the thickness of the coating is over a critical value. The critical thickness (t^*) can be derived from the principle of fracture mechanics⁽⁷⁾.

$$t^* = \frac{d_f}{2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{E_f \bar{\sigma}_c^n}{E_c \bar{\sigma}_f} \right)^\beta} - 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

whereas d_f is the diameter of the fiber, β is Weibull modulus, E_r and E_c are the Young's modulus of the fiber and the coating materials respectively, $\bar{\sigma}_f$ is the average tensile strength of the fibers, $\bar{\sigma}_c^n$ is the normalized strength of the coating.

The calculated values of t^* for some systems are shown in Table 2. So the thickness of the resistant layer should not exceed the critical value.

In the calculation mentioned above, the interface of fiber/coating was assumed to be strong and the calculated value of t^* is very small except CF/BN system. In the case of weak bonding at the interface, however, notch effect will not be caused owing to the premature debonding. The gradient form at the interface between CFs and resistant layers is necessary from the point of

specific strength and bearing ability^[3]. All of these enlighten us to observe and analyze the morphology, structure, and composite mechanism of bio-materials in the nature carefully. With a systematic analysis, we hope to find some usable regularities to be simulated for making modern materials. This may be beneficial in solving the problems existing in MMC and even in material science and technology. In the present paper, the interfaces of bio-materials in the nature (e.g. bamboo and animal bone) are observed and analyzed firstly, and then the principle of biomimetics for the interface design is proposed and an ideal model of artificial interface is designed for the chosen MMC systems, which will be the exploration of a new way to solve the interfacial problems of MMC.

2. Observation and analysis of the biomaterial interfaces of in the nature

The existence of interface between animal bone and muscle is obvious. The gradient layer is called periosteum, which consists of three layers^[4], as shown in Figure 1. The outer layer of the periosteum is mainly composed of thick collagen fibers, which intersect each other into network. The collagen fiber bundles enter into the out-circumferential lamellae to connect with bone closely by Sharpy's fibers (also called perforating fibers), which, furthermore, is a part of the tendon fibers near the part of tendon and ligament to connect muscle. The inner layer is calcified tissue and the medium part is composed mainly of few fibers (collagen fibers) as well as a number of cells, which are very active and take part in the forming of new bone while growing; After bone is stable and then broken, the cells become to osteoblast with the ability of forming bone. So we can keep in mind that the degree of calcification is increasing gradiently from the outer to the inner and the collagen fibers are decreasing gradiently. These show that the perfect match among muscle, tendon and bone take them to have the advanced properties.

Many examples can be elicited from the biomaterials that have gradient change at the interface. So the characters of the complete interfaces of bio-materials in the nature could be described as follows:

- a. good stability in the environment.
- b. gradient change and/or multi-layered change in structure, texture and/or compositions cross it.

The marvelous coordination of these characters results in the nice properties of biomaterials in the nature. Thus the interface design for man-made composites should learn from biomaterials in the nature, that is, the interface of man-made composite should have similar interface of biomaterial to form a composite with marvelous properties.

3. Biomimetic Design of Interface

The problems concerning carbon fiber reinforced metals (e.g. Al, Ti and so on) are mainly related to the interfaces of them. They are

- a. chemical reaction between carbon and metals to form unstable interfaces;
- b. poor wetting between carbon and metals;
- c. residual stress to result in undulation of their properties.

In the light of biomimetics, the gradient change on structures and/or compositions across the interfaces of composites could solve the problems caused by the poor combination of physical and chemical properties of constituents. For carbon fiber reinforced metal system, however, the gradient form from carbon to matrix could not form a stable interface. So we must remove or resist the chemical reaction at first to get a stable interface, and then let the composition or structure form the gradient change at the interface, which would overcome the shortcomings

fracture mechanism because the gradient form can readjust the bonding status between CFs and resistant layers .

3.4 Transition of layers.

The removal of original interface (fiber/matrix) results in forming three new interfaces: fiber/resistant layer, resistant layer/wetting layer and wetting layer/ matrix . The transition layer from the wetting layer to the matrix is in the form of gradient composition to meet the wetting condition at the interface. The other interfaces should also adopt the gradient form of composition and structure to avoid stress concentration .

A function ($f(z)$) can be defined to describe the gradient form of the constituent compositions at the interfaces^[8]:

$$f(Z) = \begin{cases} f_0 & 0 \leq Z \leq Z_0 \\ (f_1 - f_0) \left[\frac{(Z - Z_0)}{(Z_1 - Z_0)} \right]^n & Z_0 \leq Z \leq Z_1 \\ f_1 & Z_1 \leq Z \leq 1 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where f_0 is the starting concentration, f_1 is the ending concentration, z is dimensionless thickness and n is calculating constant.

The index n in the Eq.6 can be calculated by computer in the light of thermal conduction equation and thermal elastic equation^[8]. For example, under the condition of minimum thermal residual stress, n is about 0.4 for C-SiC system and it is about 1.9 under the minimum density.

As the results of analysis and design mentioned above, the interfacial model of carbon fiber reinforced metals by biomimetics is in the form of fiber//resistant layer//wetting layer as pyrolytic carbon (PC) //resistant layer//wetting layer, where PC is the composition of fiber and used for adjusting the interfacial shear stress, the resistant layer is composed of refractory compound such as SiC, TiC, TiB₂, AlN, TiN and so on; the wetting layer are elements or compounds which solubilize the matrix to some extent without chemical reaction, and the symbol "/" represents the gradient change on compositions across the two layers. For example, the gradient interfaces are in the form of PC//SiC//Si, PC//TiC//Ti or PC//AlN//Al for carbon fiber reinforced Al or Al-alloys, and PC//TiC//Ti, PC//TiN//Ti or PC//TiB₂//Ti for carbon fiber reinforced Ti or Ti alloys, PC//SiC//SiO₂ for CFR Mg-alloys.

The form of interface can be chosen on the basis of using matrix and fiber themselves as well as the fabrication process, while the thickness of resistant layer and gradient form can be determined by MMC equations given above. This is the process of biomimetic design of the interface for MMC.

4. Tentative experiments

In order to verify the model designed above, some tentative experiments have been carried out. Based on the design, the gradient form of PC//SiC//Si was coated on CFs by chemical vapor deposition process continuously, then aluminum was deposited by physical vapor deposition to get precursors.

After heat-treatment at 973K for 0.5hrs. CF/Al system has severe reaction to result in the decrease of tensile strength down to 50.3%. Comparing to that, the strength of the designed form of CF-PC//SiC//Si and Al precursors keeps no obvious change, which shows that the designed interface has resisted the diffusion and reaction of aluminum to carbon, improved the wetting of the system and readjusted the bonding status to achieve an effective composite

results. All these tentative experiments indicate that the designed interface is an advanced and useful one for making metal matrix composites. The further research on the properties of the precursors is being done.

5. Conclusion:

The complete interfaces of bio-materials in the nature are characterized by the stability in environment, good chemical and physical compatibility and gradient change and/or multi-layer on structure and/or composition.

On the concept of stability and gradient change or multi-layer structure, the biomimetic designed interfaces for artificial metal matrix composites is better to be in the form of fiber//resistant layer//wetting layer.

The results of the tentative experiments indicate that the interface from the biomimetic design is advantageous to MMC. And also application of the design to ceramic matrix and polymeric matrix composites can be expected.

Acknowledge

The authors are grateful to the National Natural Science Foundation of China and State Key Lab for Fatigue and Fracture Materials, IMRAS for financial support, also to Mr.Li Shihong for meaningful discussion on the structure of biomaterials.

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Fig.1. Illustration of periosteum microstructure.

Table 1 The properties of some refractory compounds

Compounds	M.P.(K)	density(g/cm ³)	α (x10 ⁻⁶ /K)	oxidation resistance*
TiB ₂	3252	4.52	8.85	2-3
ZrB ₂	3713	6.09	6.63	2-3
TiC	3433	4.94	7.4	3
SiC	2373	3.22	4.7	2
B ₄ C	2723	2.52	4.5	3
TiN	3203	5.43	9.35	3
BN	3003	2.25		2
Al ₂ O ₃	2288	3.97	8.8	1
SiO ₂	2001	2.32	9	1

*Classed according to the temperature range in which the rate of attack by air would cause severe erosion of failure of the coated specimen within a few hours: (1) above 1973K; (2) 1673-1973K; (3) 1373-1673K; (4) 1073-1373K and (5) 773-1073K.

Table 2 The critical thickness of coatings on carbon fibers

	Fiber m(GPa)	σ (MPa)	Coating m(GPa)	σ (MPa)	β	t^*
CF/SiC	260	500	470	2300	3	0.039
					6	0.0009
	400	2500	470	2300	3	0.7680
					6	0.3820
CF/B ₄ C	260	4500	470	2300	3	0.0390
					6	0.0009
	400	2500	470	2300	3	0.7680
					6	0.3820
CF/BN	260	4500	90	1400	3	1.0980
					6	0.8250
	400	2500	90	1400	3	10.68
					6	50.57
CF/TiB ₂	260	4500	510	1000	3	0.003
					6	3x10 ⁻⁶
	400	2500	510	1000	3	0.054
					6	0.002
CF/AlB ₂	260	4500	420	700	3	1.56x10 ⁻³
					6	1.39x10 ⁻⁶
	400	2500	420	700	3	0.037
					6	6.29x10 ⁻⁴
CF/TiC	260	4500	450	1400	3	0.010
					6	5.9x10 ⁻⁵
	400	2500	450	1400	3	0.209
					6	0.0265